

Food cultures: co-creation and evaluation of a thesaurus as a cultural infrastructure

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Close collaboration with societal actors is a central part of the Digital Humanities project exploreAT! (exploring austria's culture through the language glass). Digital tools have increasingly enabled the process of interconnecting and opening up various resources across different media. To make use of this potential, exploreAT! cooperates with the Topothek, a citizen driven digital infrastructure which collects local historical multimedia items from private sources. It is of interest to connect this collection to exploreAT! as it contains a variety of cultural and local historical information, which can only be accessed with the help of citizens and their knowledge. To initiate such collaboration, both scientists and citizens need to learn how to interact with each other in order to constitute common goals. In this paper, we focus on the workflow and process established. We introduce the community group "Topothek", a citizen driven archival platform to archive, annotate, geo-reference and present regional culture. We present our first co-created result, a food cultures thesaurus, interlinking food terms with cultural practices and tools. The added value for Topothek is increased discoverability, while for exploreAT! it is the scientific exploitation for cultural lexicography of the multimedia archive. The processes along the mutual learning scenarios are evaluated. The co-created thesaurus is co-funded by the DARIAH-theme 2017 "public humanities" in collaboration with ADAPT centre Dublin (Ireland).